

Project video D13.5

Authors:

Chiara Canestrini, Gianluca Dolfi

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PU	Public	x
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	

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About OneNet

OneNet will provide a seamless integration of all the actors in the electricity network across Europe to create the conditions for a synergistic operation that optimizes the overall energy system while creating an open and fair market structure.

The project OneNet (One Network for Europe) is funded through the EU's eighth Framework Programme Horizon 2020. It is titled "TSO – DSO Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation" and responds to the call "Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future (LC)".

While the electrical grid is moving from being a fully centralized to a highly decentralized system, grid operators have to adapt to this changing environment and adjust their current business model to accommodate faster reactions and adaptive flexibility. This is an unprecedented challenge requiring an unprecedented solution. For this reason, the two major associations of grid operators in Europe, ENTSO-E and EDSO, have activated their members to put together a unique consortium.

OneNet will see the participation of a consortium of over 70 partners. Key partners in the consortium include: already mentioned ENTSO-E and EDSO, Elering, EDP Distribution, RWTH Aachen University, University of Comillas, VITO, European Dynamics, Ubitech, Engineering, and the EU's Florence School of Regulation (Energy).

The key elements of the project are:

1. Definition of a common market design for Europe: this means standardized products and key parameters for grid services which aim at the coordination of all actors, from grid operators to customers;
2. Definition of a Common IT Architecture and Common IT Interfaces: this means not trying to create a single IT platform for all the products but enabling an open architecture of interactions among several platforms so that anybody can join any market across Europe; and
3. Large-scale demonstrators to implement and showcase the scalable solutions developed throughout the project. These demonstrators are organized in four clusters coming to include countries in every region of Europe and testing innovative use cases never validated before.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
FSR	Florence School of Regulation
WP13	Work Package 13

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the project video, which will become a key reference for the stakeholder engagement, exploitation, dissemination, communication and standardization activities of OneNet. One of the main advantages of using video as a means to promote the project is its unique ability to provide a tangible, visual and concise summary of the project's principle goals in a short space of time. Similarly, being a product that is highly agile in terms of its shareability and watchability, it is hoped that it will reach a very wide and diverse audience, from senior policy makers to the general public.

WP13 is responsible for dissemination, communication, and standardization activities and, therefore, it has crosscutting roles across all other project work packages. Equally, this deliverable is one that can be used by all project partners. For these reasons, all work packages have been involved in, and contributed to, a multifaceted review of this deliverable.

This deliverable is organized as follows: Section 1 provides a brief introduction to the video; Section 2 presents the video and defines the channels for its promotion.

LINK TO THE VIDEO ON YOUTUBE: <https://youtu.be/MLXPyAzy74s>

[DOWNLOAD THE VIDEO HERE](#)

1 Introduction

The reasoning behind the production of the OneNet project video is three-fold:

- developing an institutional video will help raise awareness on the project and reach a wider audience;
- a promo-educational video can create consensus and acceptance of the solutions proposed by conveying a simple and effective message; and
- communication and dissemination activities will highly benefit from the support of video and multimedia content, as it is more attractive and engaging than other outputs.

Each of the main communication tasks take a different approach in order to complement each other. The project video will become a new key element for the project identity, together with: the corporate identity, document templates, brochure and the website. The project website provides clear and engaging information about the project activities and events and gathers the project's public findings. The website is constantly updated and benefits from a strong connection with the social media channels. The website also hosts a project blog, which will feature valuable insights from the sector, including contributions from the partners. This video will act as an initial focal point for anyone visiting the website, and will equally be shared widely through all social media channels and alike.

Task 13.2 covers the communication and outreach activities aimed at reaching a more general audience. Specific actions are: creating and managing a new, dedicated database; developing a project video; creating awareness of the project through social media (LinkedIn, Twitter); producing articles, interviews and webinars to be published on the project website; preparing newsletters to be distributed to the OneNet database; and supporting project partners in contributing to the project blog.

1.1 Target Audience

The target audience has been identified based on a number of factors, including: analysis of audiences from previous projects implemented by the consortium, mapping of partners and stakeholders, and research of similar projects external to the consortium.

The key audience groups have been identified as follows:

- System Operators (TSOs, DSOs);
- Energy Regulators;
- Policy Makers;
- Aggregators;
- ICT, IoT providers;

- Market operators;
- Academia;
- Consumers (Industry, Prosumers and energy communities, EU Citizens);
- Power Producers; and
- Energy Suppliers.

Some of the ways that the project will further identify audiences and create a “user persona” include:

- Customer surveys;
- Research similar projects and topics;
- Collection of demographic data from OneNet’s website analytics; and
- Analysis of newsletter subscribers and social media followers.

1.2 Concept of the video

In a fast-moving world challenged by climate change, the electricity sector plays a key role in reaching a decarbonised, sustainable and smart future. What will the European electricity system of the future look like?

The idea behind the video is to invite the audience to imagine:

- A new generation of grid services able to fully exploit demand response, storage and distributed generation;
- Citizens at the centre of the energy transition unlocking existing and new solutions to create fair, transparent and open conditions for the consumer; and
- One Network for Europe as a system of systems approach to the European electricity system supported by a unique IT architecture.

The smart future evoked in the first part of the video is linked to the OneNet project which will make it possible in the second part. Thanks to OneNet the future is already present.

1.3 Corporate identity

As part of task 13.1. General communication and dissemination activities, the EUI as WP13 leader, together with the other project partners, defined the project corporate identity and produced the first presentation materials. The project logo was selected by the consortium during the first general assembly in October 2020

from a selection of proposals developed by the EUI. The logo aims to bring the message of the project together in a simple design that can be easily presented through a number of different mediums.

The new video complements the corporate identity of OneNet, now including:

- Project logo and tagline;
- Corporate identity and guidelines;
- Project brochure;
- Project templates (word and power point);
- Virtual backgrounds and other digital graphics; and
- Project video.

2 Video and communications plan

2.1 Key communication goals and actions of OneNet

The project is directing its communications efforts towards the following goals:

- Promote the activities and the results of the project;
- Identify, reach, and engage with stakeholders;
- Improve fruitful synergies and internal communication between the work packages;
- Drive and support innovation in the grid services market;
- Make the produced knowledge more accessible, inclusive, and actionable;
- Facilitate interaction and feedback/input on our work; and
- Improve press & media relations.

Where possible, all resources will be available in open access.

2.2 Key messages of the project

In the external communications flow, the scope of the project translates the key messages that are disseminated through the different channels:

- OneNet aims at removing the entry barriers to the flex market and ensuring seamless coordination between grid and market operation;
- OneNet aims to create unique synergies between all players at EU and national level; and
- OneNet is more than a project: it's also a platform of cooperation.

Communication channels through which our key messages are disseminated to the stakeholders:

- Website: <https://onenet-project.eu/>;
- Newsletter;
- GRIFOn;
- Social media;
 - OneNet Twitter;
 - OneNet LinkedIn;
- Public relations (i.e. press);
- Partners' websites; and
- Webinars / LIVE and Online Events.

The scheduling of communication activities followed the timing of all of the project's deliverables:

- New publications;
- Milestones;
- Events;
- News from the project network;
- Consultations; and
- GRIFOn activities.

Regular statistics on the impact of the website and social media are gathered and analysed by the WP13 leaders, helping the project coordinator and partners revise and improve the communication strategy.

WP13 facilitates and supports the participation in main events in the field by doing preliminary research to find the best forums to disseminate the project and network; creating dedicated promo material; doing live coverage of the events on the website and social media; actively engaging with journalists and event organisers and launching partnerships to maximise the communications outreach.

2.3 The project video

Taking into account the goals and key messages of the project, a 1.50-minute video has been designed and produced to convey the same vision to a wider audience. The process included:

- original script;
- storyboard;
- voice over recording; and
- video production.

Figure 1 Video frame

Figure 2 Frame from storyboard

The video will be released via the FSR YouTube channel and a downloadable link.

[The video can be downloaded here](#)

2.4 Channels to promote the video

The video will be launched in coordination with the partners and promoted via:

- OneNet Website;
- OneNet Social media: LinkedIn and Twitter;
- OneNet Newsletter; and
- Network and websites of the Project Partners.

